

Investigating changes in the chemical composition of liquid during polymer tube processing by SDBD

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The technique aimed to achieve uniform atmospheric pressure plasma treatment of inner and/or outer surfaces of polymeric tubes and other hollow bodies was developed by combining basic features of the Surface Dielectric Barrier Discharge (SDBD) and the plasmas in contact with liquids. Such configuration is favorable for the continual treatment of polymers. It could be used, for example, in processes such as activation and coating of biomedical devices, sterilization, cleaning, surface modification, etc.

This combined cold plasma discharge operating on the boundary of solid-liquid-gas holds great promise for industrial applications, yet a thorough investigation of its potential drawbacks is essential. Plasma, under specific conditions, can alter polymer materials by causing melting, etching, or even destruction. While in our previous studies, the damage of polymer tubes was not observed, dedicated experiments under well-defined conditions are necessary to investigate the changes in the chemical composition of the used liquids.

In this research, we conducted an examination and quantification of species present in the liquid phase produced during the processing of specific polymers by the SDBD. Using the HPLC technique, we quantified the amount of plasticizer leached from the inner surface of the tubes after plasma treatment. It was observed that while the amount of leached plasticizer from the polyvinyl chloride (PVC) tube increased with increasing treatment time and power, negligible amounts of by-products from polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) degradation were detected for longer treatment times. Also, we examined the inner surfaces of tubes both pre- and post-plasma treatment. Understanding the effects of material plasma processing is critical for ensuring the safety and effectiveness of plasma-based processes in industrial applications.

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